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A new species of *Argoptochus* WEISE, 1883 (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Entiminae: Phyllobiini) from Turkey

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Abstract: *Argoptochus anatolicus* sp. n. from western Turkey is described. Its systematic position within the genus is unclear, it displays some significant characters typical of Anatolian species e.g. *A. reitteri* FORMANEK, 1908. For the first time, the whole female genital tract is described and depicted in *Argoptochus*. The determination of the new species with use of the key by BOROVEC (2006) encounters unsurmountable problems caused by unique combination of characters in *A. anatolicus*.

Key words: Coleoptera, Curculionidae, taxonomy, new species, *Argoptochus*; Turkey.

INTRODUCTION

The phyllobiine genus *Argoptochus* WEISE, 1883 now comprises 36 (sub)species placed, except for the nominal subgenus, in three subgenera: *Foucartidius* PESARINI, 1981, *Mylacoptochus* PESARINI, 1981, and *Neohenschia* KOROTYAEV, 1992 (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). Since these subgenera have never been comprehensively treated taxonomically and require basic revision, they are not considered in this paper. A large majority of *Argoptochus* species is known from the Balkans, only seven are known to occur in Turkey. Another Turkish species is described below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Body length was measured from the anterior margin of the eyes to the elytral apex. Rostrum length was measured from the anterior margin of the eyes to the anterior part of the epistome. Unless otherwise stated, the width of the rostrum is defined as the pterygial span, i.e. the distance between the outer margins of the pterygia. The statement “pterygia projecting” means that pterygia are extending from the outline of the rostrum in dorsal view, whereas “pterygia distant” denotes a condition in which the anterior margin of the pterygia are clearly located behind the anterior margin of the rostrum between the mandibles and the pterygia. Various areas of legs, dorsal and ventral margins in particular, are described as if legs were stretched horizontally at right angle to longitudinal body axis, what allows for

a precise terminology. Modified insertions of setae along the ventral wall of tibiae forming usually pointed tubercles are hereby termed (tibial) spines. The enlarged terminal (proximal) end of the spiculum ventrale is named caput in the text. Although aedeagus is defined, as generally accepted, as pedon with apodemes, the two terms i.e. aedeagus and pedon are used interchangeably, depending on the context, particularly while taking measurements. The same approach applies to the female 8th sternite. Therefore terms such as “plate/lamella of 8th sternite” are rejected. “\” separates label data of different specimens. Since the border between frons and epifrons is completely unclear in large majority of Entiminae species, we prefer to apply more general term “dorsal wall of rostrum” (=frons + epifrons). Unless otherwise stated, length of funicle and tarsal segments and measured without basal condyle. We abandoned, after Białooki, in press, terms that traditionally were used to describe certain sectors of spermatheca e.g. ramus, nodulus, collum, which were often used interchangeably, and replaced them with gland- and duct-lobe, concise and self evident terms that need no explanation.

Dissected terminalia of both sexes are stored in a microvial with glycerine pinned under the card bearing the specimen (occasionally, damaged parts are glued to this card).

The photographs were taken with JVC KYF75 digital camera attached to Leica M205C stereomicroscope and stacked using the AutoMontage software by Syncroscopy.

Acronyms: BIAL – collection of P.Z. Białooki, Sopot, Poland; KSÜ – collection of Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Turkey; USMB – collection of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, Poland; WANA – collection of Marek Wanat, Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, Poland. Holotype is abbreviated as “ht”.

RESULTS

Subfamily Entiminae SCHOENHERR, 1823

Tribe Phyllobiini SCHOENHERR, 1826

Genus *Argoptochus* WEISE, 1883 (type species *Peritelus bisignatus* GERMAR, 1823).

Argoptochus anatolicus sp. n.

<https://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/5739B1FC-A2CD-4E63-A89F-9A1B1716D227>

(Figs. 1–10)

Material examined: holotype male, dissected: 22.05.2009 C Turkey, Mt.1003 m N Tuz Lake; 39.1317N, 33.3465E, leg. P.Z. Białooki [BIAL]. Paratypes: as ht, 6 exx.\ 03.06.2024 C Turkey NE Tölköy, 1010 m, SE Gölbaşı SSE Ankara 39.6603N, 33.0356E, leg. P.Z. Białooki, 12 exx. [BIAL; BORO; KSÜ; USMB; WANA].

Diagnosis. The new species (Fig. 1) cannot be obviously referred to any species group (subgenus) hitherto known, although according to R. Borovec (e-mail comm.) it is most similar to *A. subsignatus* (BOHEMAN, 1834). However, this similarity seems superficial since certain characters significant phylogenetically e.g. densely scaled abdomen (Fig. 8), and structure of spermatheca, as well as general structure of female genital tract (Fig. 9) seem to suggest closer affinity to Anatolian species. Amongst these species it is recognizable at first glance by very densely arranged yellow-green recumbent scales; lack of conspicuous raised elytral scales; very broad dorsal wall of rostrum (Fig. 2); and scrobes shortly extended backwardly behind pterygia. On the other hand, *A. anatolicus* sp. n. is similar to *A. reitteri* FORMANEK, 1908. The two species share similar body size and shape; very broad dorsal wall of rostrum, head constricted behind eyes, extended scrobes, strongly sclerotized aedeagus, and spermatheca with strongly reduced both gland- and duct-lobes (Fig. 10). *A. anatolicus*

differs from *A. reitteri* mainly in lack of strongly raised elytral scales; in recumbent elytral scales clearly elongate; in second funicle segment slightly longer than segments 3 and 4 combined, whereas in *A. reitteri* segment 2 is clearly shorter than next two segments combined; in disparate shape of aedeagus; spermatheca with minute, but nevertheless clearly developed duct-lobe.

Since subgenera proposed by PESARINI (1981), and REITTER (1906) [KOROTYAEV & EGOROV (1979) only proposed a replacement name] require a basic revision, they are not applied in this paper.

Description (male).

Body length 2.2-3.0 mm (ht 2.35 mm); males much smaller than females. Body black; legs and antennae light red-brown, except for dark brown femora with lighter distal parts.

Head (Fig. 2) very wide, strongly transverse, covered with dense, weakly elongate, recumbent, yellow scales obscuring finely, densely punctate body surface, and with longer scales, weakly raised, narrow, distinctly widened apicad, directed towards central point on vertex much behind hind margins of eyes; clearly constricted behind eyes; interocular area twice as broad as longitudinal diameter of an eye, distinctly convex transversally; central fovea not visible; eyes moderately large, weakly elongate, moderately convex, distinctly projecting; temples clearly shorter than an eye diameter.

Rostrum short, transverse ($1.35 \times$), conically narrowed (Fig. 2); dorsal wall very wide, clearly narrowed backwardly, indistinctly separated from, and practically in level with interocular area, in narrowest point 0.6 total width of rostrum in middle, with distinct although shallow median sulcus; lateral margins of dorsal wall disappear far before anterior margins of eyes; epistome moderately large, weakly delimited, bare; the rest of anterior part of the dorsal wall (anteriorly of antennal insertions) with strongly reduced vestiture (Fig. 2); scrobes shortly extended backwards behind pterygia, well visible from above.

Antennae (Fig. 3) slender; scape slightly shorter than funicle, weakly but distinctly arched, moderately, gradually expanded distally, covered with recumbent semierect narrow elongate scales and similar but somewhat broader, recumbent scales; first funicle segment twice longer than wide; second slightly less elongate, distinctly shorter than first segment, slightly longer than segments 3 and 4 combined; segments 3-5 isodiametric; segments 6-7 weakly transverse; club fusiform, $2.2 \times$ longer than broad, as long as four distal funicle segments combined, almost $1.5 \times$ broader than last funicle segment, clearly broader than scape; base narrow, almost linearly, fairly weakly widened.

Prothorax (Fig. 1) distinctly ($1.3 \times$ wider than long) transverse, rather weakly convex longitudinally, moderately convex transversally; sides moderately arcuate; broadest indistinctly behind middle; weakly but perceptibly, broadly constricted along anterior margin, which is somewhat arcuately expanded anteriorly and distinctly narrower than base of pronotum; covered with dense, clearly elongate, oval, yellowish scales obscuring body surface nearly completely, and with slightly raised, narrow, elongate scales; both recumbent and raised scales directed anteriorly to central point on anterior margin.

Elytra (Fig. 1) distinctly elongate, $1.4 \times$ longer than wide, $2.7 \times$ longer, and $1.45 \times$ broader than prothorax; basally with well-developed vertical wall; regularly rounded laterally, broadest in middle; apex fairly broadly rounded; longitudinally rather weakly convex, declivity weakly convex, subvertical only in short distance to apex; striae very narrow, subequally broad as width of recumbent elytral scales, punctures elongate, interspaces somewhat shorter, each puncture covered with inconspicuous, weakly raised hair subequally long as length of

recumbent elytral scales; interstices flat, 4-6 × broader than striae, covered with irregular 4-6 rows of rather weakly elongate, oval, recumbent, yellowish scales completely obscuring surface, and with slightly raised, elongate, narrow scales, distributed irregularly, slightly longer than length of recumbent scales; scales slightly more raised on apical declivity.

Legs fairly slender, sparsely covered with small, recumbent scales, and with weakly raised narrow scales; dorsal margin of protibia straight; ventral margin without spines; tarsi moderately robust, second segment of protarsus slightly elongate; third tarsite 1.5 × broader than long, 1.5 × broader than preceding segment; projecting part of onychium clearly shorter than length of third tarsite; metatarsi distinctly more slender, with relatively longer onychium (projecting section subequally long as length of preceding segment).

Ventrites (Fig. 8) densely covered with oval recumbent scales largely obscuring surface, and with narrow, raised scales; male 8th hemisternites fairly small, broadly separated (Fig. 4).

Aedeagus (Fig. 5) strongly sclerotized; apodemes much longer than, and weakly delimited from pedon, strongly, gradually widened proximally; ring of tegmen strongly extended, parameres subequally long as ring diameter, basal half fused, apical parts rather strongly diverging, distance between apices clearly longer than pedon width; apodeme very thin, subequally long as ring diameter; lateral margins of dorsal wall rather broad, broadest in pedon middle; apical part subparallel-sided, apex fairly strongly tapering, top broadly rounded; in lateral view moderately arched, dorsal margin stronger so (Fig. 6).

Females (Fig. 7) clearly differ from males in on average larger body; more robust, stronger convex elytra; legs slightly more slender; last ventrite somewhat longer, more narrowly rounded.

Female genital tract (Fig. 9) peculiar; ovipositor very short, weakly sclerotized, moderately pigmented; 8th sternite minute, spiculum ventrale very long, together with sternite as long as ovipositor with vagina, without caput; vagina relatively thick, typically for Phyllobiini, strongly transversally corrugated; bursa extraordinary long and slender, divided into several morphologically different sections; proximal section only indistinctly enlarged, in contrast to some European species (only several species were examined) showing proximal end of bursa subglobose, several times broader than distal part; duct inserted subapically, in a very strong contrast to virtually all Entiminae, far distant from insertion of common oviduct; its distal section fairly strongly, gradually enlarged (Fig. 10). Spermatheca (Fig. 10) with large cornu, distinctly longer than corpus; gland-lobe hardly detectable, duct-lobe minute, thin. Since preliminary results of examination of soft parts of female terminalia turned out very promising, further analyses are highly desired. In strongly derived forms, showing high level of homoplasy, the anatomical structures are most significant phylogenetically, the general rule also true in Entiminae.

Ecology. All specimens were swept in extremely hot and dry steppe close to the northernmost part of Tuz Lake, at foothill of Mt. 1003 m during hot and sunny day; no specimen was collected at higher altitude. Near Tölköy collected by sweeping small areas of dry steppe amongst arable ground in late afternoon.

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Fig. 1. *Argoptochus anatolicus* male holotype.

Fig. 2. *Argoptochus anatolicus* male head.

Fig. 3. *Argoptochus anatolicus* male antenna.

Fig. 4. *Argoptochus anatolicus* male 8th hemisternites.

Fig. 5. *Argoptochus anatolicus* male aedeagus dorsal view.

Fig. 6. *Argoptochus anatolicus* male aedeagus lateral view.

Fig. 7. *Argoptochus anatolicus* female.

Fig. 8. *Argoptochus anatolicus* female ventrites.

Fig. 9. *Argoptochus anatolicus* female terminalia.

Fig. 10. *Argoptochus anatolicus* female bursa apex and spermatheca.

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